

A Systematic Literature Review of Quantum Machine Learning and Its Applications

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we conduct a focused, PRISMA-style systematic screening of recent QML research by restricting the scope to SCI/SCI-Expanded journal articles published between 2023–2025 (including early access articles for 2026). The initial search yielded 74 records across six widely used digital libraries and publisher platforms; after removing 4 duplicates, screening titles/abstracts (19 exclusions), and assessing full texts (21 exclusions), 30 articles were retained for in-depth thematic and taxonomic synthesis. The reviewed literature covers variational quantum circuits, quantum kernel methods, hybrid quantum-classical models, quantum annealing approaches, federated QML architectures, data encoding strategies, and adversarial robustness analyses. The findings indicate that QML models can exhibit stronger representational capacity and higher generalization performance compared to classical methods, particularly on high-dimensional, noisy, or small sample datasets. Reported results in domains such as healthcare, chemistry, energy systems, cybersecurity, blockchain, and finance reveal the diversity of QML applications and its interdisciplinary potential. Nevertheless, the limited qubit capacity of current NISQ hardware, constraints on circuit depth, and noise-related issues remain fundamental factors that restrict the scalability of QML models. This study synthesizes methodological trends, identifies open research problems, and proposes a directional roadmap for future QML research focused on hardware-aware circuit design, efficient data encoding schemes, and robust learning frameworks. The final corpus size is primarily driven by deliberate scope restrictions (SCI/SCI-Expanded journals only, 2023–2025 window with early-access 2026 items, exclusion of conference papers/preprints), rather than by a lack of available QML publications.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in quantum technologies have initiated a transformation that redefines the limits of classical computing architectures, and Quantum Machine Learning (QML) has emerged as a key component of this transformation [1]. By combining machine learning algorithms with quantum information processing capabilities, QML offers a novel approach to high-dimensional, complex, and computationally expensive problems where traditional methods struggle. The parallel processing capacity of quantum circuits, the expressive power of quantum states, and the ability to naturally represent nonlinear transformations in a quantum setting enable QML models to provide alternative solutions, especially for problems that require big data analytics, highly interactive systems, and high-dimensional optimization

[7], [12].

In recent years, QML-based models have been explored across multiple application areas including healthcare, chemistry, energy systems, finance, security, network management, and blockchain ecosystems, highlighting the interdisciplinary relevance of the field [3]–[6], [8]. Rather than claiming exhaustive coverage of all QML outputs (e.g., conferences and preprints), this survey provides a focused and reproducible synthesis of recent journal-level evidence by systematically screening SCI/SCI-Expanded journal articles published in 2023–2025 (including early-access 2026 items) using an explicit multi-stage protocol. The review consolidates findings along methodological families, application domains, evaluation practices, and recurring limitations, with the goal of identifying consistent patterns, gaps, and emerging trends that can guide future research and deployment-oriented work [11], [19].

1.1. General Background

QML, as an approach that integrates the structural properties of quantum mechanics into machine learning processes, represents a significant break in the computational paradigm. Quantum phenomena such as superposition and entanglement enable data representations that are difficult to achieve with classical information processing methods; this creates new opportunities especially for modeling complex distributions, accelerating optimization problems, and performing efficient search in high-dimensional spaces [1], [7].

Despite the limitations of the NISQ era, models such as variational quantum circuits, quantum neural networks, and quantum kernel methods have quickly attracted the attention of a large research community and their applicability has been tested on prototype hardware [9], [15], [16]. Results reported in various application domains demonstrate that QML not only offers theoretical potential but can also produce more efficient or more interpretable solutions than classical models under certain conditions.

This trend is supported by the increasing number of QML-based approaches applied to tasks such as healthcare data analysis [3], molecular energy level estimation [4], state estimation and anomaly detection in energy grids [5], detection of network security threats [8], and risk assessment in smart contracts [6]. This broad adoption shows that QML has become a strategic research area that bridges computational science and applied disciplines.

1.2. Trends and Requirements in the Literature

A review of the current literature reveals that QML research is shaped along two main axes: method-oriented studies and application-oriented evaluations. Method-oriented studies focus on topics such as quantum circuit optimization, noise mitigation strategies, the capacity of data encoding schemes, model generalization capabilities, and the stability of training processes [9], [10], [17].

These works play a fundamental role in understanding the impact of physical limitations of quantum devices on algorithmic performance and in developing more efficient models. In parallel, application-oriented studies show that QML can produce competitive results in different disciplines despite limited qubit capacity, circuit depth constraints, and hardware noise. Prominent examples of these trends include biomarker analysis in health informatics [3], molecular system computation in materials science [4], [18], anomaly detection in energy management [5], attack classification in cybersecurity [8], and evaluation of financial risk models [29], [30].

This study provides a focused and reproducible synthesis of recent Quantum Machine Learning (QML) advances by systematically screening SCI/SCI-Expanded journal articles published in 2023–2025 (including early-access 2026 items) using an explicit multi-stage pro-

tocol. Rather than claiming exhaustive coverage of all QML outputs (e.g., conferences and preprints), the analysis prioritizes methodologically mature journal studies and consolidates them into a coherent taxonomy of methods, application domains, and recurring constraints to identify consistent trends and actionable research gaps. Accordingly, the final corpus size should be interpreted as a consequence of strict eligibility constraints (SCI/SCI-Expanded journals only, exclusion of conferences/preprints, and full-text accessibility) rather than as an indicator of limited activity in QML. This focused scope improves comparability across studies and strengthens the reproducibility of the resulting taxonomy and cross-domain synthesis.

1.3. Contributions of This Study

This survey provides five main contributions to the Quantum Machine Learning (QML) literature through a focused and reproducible synthesis based on an explicit screening and classification protocol:

- A focused interdisciplinary literature map is provided. Studies published in SCI/SCI-Expanded indexed journals across diverse application domains such as health informatics, chemical modeling, energy systems, cybersecurity, financial analysis, smart contracts, and optimization problems are evaluated within a unified framework, making the breadth of QML applications systematically visible.
- QML methods, architectures, and computational models are taxonomically classified. Variational quantum circuits, quantum neural networks, quantum kernel methods, hybrid quantum–classical models, federated QML architectures, and adversarially robust optimization strategies are organized according to their architectural characteristics and intended use.
- Performance trends reported across application domains are comparatively analyzed. The advantages, limitations, computational costs, and performance improvements of QML models over classical methods are evaluated to identify application-oriented trends, opportunities, and bottlenecks.
- Open research problems and future research directions are identified. Critical challenges such as qubit scalability, noise management, circuit depth limitations, optimization of data encoding strategies, adversarial robustness, model generalization capacity, and real-world adaptability are highlighted, and a solution-oriented roadmap is proposed.
- A meta-level synthesis and practical guidance is provided. Beyond individual study outcomes, the review integrates model families, encoding strategies, optimization behavior, and hardware constraints across domains, identifying scenarios in which QML is competitive and translating these insights into actionable design principles for scalable and robust QML systems.

2. Methodology

This study employs a systematic review approach to examine the Quantum Machine Learning (QML) literature from an interdisciplinary perspective. The methodology adopted is aligned with the steps proposed in previous surveys and reviews of QML, and consists of structured stages for database selection, search strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and thematic-taxonomic analysis of the literature [1], [7], [11], [12], [19], [21].

2.1. Databases and Search Strategy

The literature search was conducted using six widely used digital libraries and publisher platforms that provide access to peer-reviewed journal content: IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, MDPI, Wiley Online Library, and Taylor & Francis Online. Within each platform, we restricted results to journal research articles (excluding conference proceedings and non-article items where possible via built-in filters) and then applied the eligibility criteria during title/abstract and full-text screening. These sources were used to identify high-impact QML studies [1], [7], [11], [12]. During the search process, a broad corpus of publications was obtained by combining keywords such as “quantum machine learning”, “variational quantum circuits”, “quantum neural networks”, “quantum kernels”, “hybrid quantum-classical models”, “quantum annealing”, “federated quantum learning”, and “quantum security” [1], [7], [19], [21]. The keyword selection was structured to cover both method types (VQC, kernel, annealing, QNN, federated QML, adversarial QML) and application domains (healthcare, chemistry, energy, security, finance, materials science, etc.).

2.2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The publications included in this study satisfy the following criteria:

- The topic is directly related to QML methods or applications.
- The publication is a peer-reviewed journal article indexed in SCI or SCI-Expanded.
- The publication date is between 2023 and 2025, including early access articles for 2026.
- The work is not a conference paper, technical report, or preprint.

These criteria aim to focus on methodologically mature journal articles that reflect the current state of QML research [1], [11], [12], [19]. The exclusion criteria were defined as follows:

- Publications that only address theoretical quantum information processing models without introducing a QML approach,
- Studies without full-text access,
- Duplicate publications or works with methodologically insufficient evaluations.

This approach enabled a focus on the methodological and experimental components of QML applications reported in the literature, allowing for an effective evaluation of the practical impact of the field [1], [7], [19].

2.3. Article Selection Process

Publications obtained from the database search were first subjected to a preliminary screening based on title and abstract, and then those deemed suitable were examined in full text [11], [12]. At this stage, methodological adequacy, application scope, dataset characteristics, and the originality of the QML approach were taken into account.

Following the final evaluation, thirty articles representing various domains such as healthcare, chemistry, energy, security, finance, kernel methods, optimization, data encoding, and adversarial analysis were selected for in-depth analysis [1]–[6], [8]–[10], [13], [16]–[19], [21], [22], [25], [26], [28] – [30]. This selection was designed to capture both the methodological and application driven diversity of the QML ecosystem.

2.4. Analysis Approach

The literature analysis was carried out at two levels: thematic and taxonomic. In the thematic analysis, the studies were classified according to their application domains (health, chemistry, energy systems, cybersecurity, blockchain and smart contracts, finance and credit scoring, image processing, materials science, and scientometric analyses) [2]–[6], [8], [13], [18], [25], [29].

In the taxonomic analysis, QML models were examined under key categories such as variational circuits, kernel methods, quantum annealing models, hybrid architectures, federated QML, adversarial QML, data encoding strategies, and optimization approaches [1], [7], [9], [10], [16], [17], [19], [21], [22], [26], [30]. This approach made it possible to reveal methodological similarities and differences across studies and to construct a structured and reproducible taxonomy of the journal-level QML landscape within the defined scope. The final corpus size ($n = 30$) reflects deliberate scope restrictions (SCI/SCI-Expanded journal-only, 2023–2025 plus early-access 2026) and an explicit multi-stage screening pipeline reported in Fig. 1 (74 identified, 4 duplicates removed, 70 screened, 19 excluded at title/abstract, 51 full texts assessed, and 21 excluded at full-text review) to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

2.5. Comparative Evaluation Approach

In this study, the literature analysis was conducted using a method-oriented and domain-oriented comparative framework. The thirty reviewed articles were first classified according to the QML approach used (VQC, quantum kernel methods, quantum annealing, QNN models, federated QML, adversarial analysis, optimization strategies, and data encoding techniques) [1], [2], [4], [5], [7], [9], [10], [13], [16], [17], [19], [21], [22], [26], [28], [29], [30].

Each work was then systematically compared in terms of target application domain, type of data used, model performance metrics, computational cost, and reported limitations [1]–[6], [8]–[10], [13], [18], [21], [25], [28], [29]. This approach made it possible to comparatively evaluate not only the results of different QML studies but also their fundamental methodological choices and the impact of these choices in application contexts.

In particular, performance and scalability differences among models developed for similar problem types were highlighted, and the conditions under which models offer advantages or suffer from limitations were analyzed from a holistic perspective [1]–[5], [8]–[10], [21], [25], [29]. The findings show that QML methods provide clear advantages in some areas (such as biomedical signal processing or molecular energy prediction), while in other cases quantum hardware limitations prevent them from matching the performance of classical methods [2]–[4], [18], [19].

This comparative evaluation framework provides the theoretical foundation for the domain-based analyses presented in subsequent sections and ensures a coherent interpretation of general trends in the QML literature. In addition, the studies were examined along five commonly used evaluation dimensions in the literature: methodological structure (algorithmic approach), application domain, performance metrics, computational cost, and limitations related to quantum hardware [1], [7], [11], [12], [19]. This multidimensional evaluation framework allowed for more objective and reproducible comparisons across studies.

2.6. Flow Diagram of the Systematic Literature Review Process

Systematic reviews in QML demonstrate that literature analysis requires a multi-layered process involving data source selection, keyword strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and thematic classification [12], [19].

The methodology used in this study follows this structured approach, which has been proposed in previous large-scale QML surveys. [Figure 1](#) presents the customized version of this methodological framework as applied in the present work. In the first stage, relevant databases were searched; subsequently, keyword-based queries were used to identify candidate publications.

Filtering by year, topic relevance, SCI/SCI-Expanded index status, and article type enabled a rigorous and controlled narrowing of the literature. In the final stage, the retained studies were classified by methodological structure and application domains, and then systematically analyzed to support transparent cross-study synthesis [12], [19].

Moreover, as the scope of QML research continues to expand, additional validation steps were incorporated to maintain methodological coherence across the review process. Each study was examined not only in terms of its bibliographic information but also its underlying research objective, model design, dataset characteristics, and experimental procedures. This ensured that the analysis captured both the conceptual foundations and practical implementations of QML methods, offering a deeper understanding of their strengths, limitations, and methodological soundness.

Furthermore, the classification stage was enhanced by organizing the selected works along multiple analytical dimensions. Studies were grouped by model architecture—such as variational quantum circuits, quantum neural networks, support vector machines, or autoencoders—as well as by optimization strategy, data encoding method, and scalability characteristics. Ultimately, this structured evaluation provides clearer and evidence-grounded synthesis of the field’s current state and supports the identification of promising future research directions.

Fig. 1. PRISMA-style flow diagram of the study selection process (identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion) with record counts at each stage. The diagram is reported to enable traceability and reproducibility of the selection process.

Figure 1 reports the record counts at each stage of the review process. The initial database search yielded 74 records, and 4 duplicate entries were removed, resulting in 70 unique records. After title/abstract screening, 19 records were excluded and 51 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility. During full-text assessment, 21 articles were excluded based on the predefined criteria, resulting in a final corpus of 30 included studies for synthesis. Full-text exclusions ($n = 21$) mainly occurred due to non-eligibility with SCI/SCI-Expanded journal status, insufficient methodological detail for comparative synthesis, non-QML focus despite keyword matches, or lack of accessible full text.

Figure 1 summarizes the systematic literature review approach employed in this work. In the first stage, databases related to the QML field were searched, and a broad set of publications was obtained by keyword-based queries. Initial filtering was then performed using criteria such as publication year, topic relevance, SCI/SCI-Expanded index status, and journal article type. Eligible studies were evaluated based on abstracts and full texts, and a final set of 30 articles was selected. In the last stage, the studies were classified by method, application domain, and model type, and a holistic analysis was conducted [11], [12], [18], [19].

3. Quantum Machine Learning Literature Review

This section examines thirty SCI/SCI-Expanded journal articles on Quantum Machine Learning (QML) within an interdisciplinary framework. The studies considered include topics such as variational quantum circuits (VQC), quantum kernel methods, quantum annealing models, quantum neural networks (QNN), federated QML, adversarial robustness analyses, data encoding strategies, optimization approaches, and a wide range of application domains [1]–[6], [8]–[10], [13], [16]–[19], [21], [22], [25], [26], [28]–[30].

A holistic examination of the literature reveals that QML is not confined to narrow problem categories but is rapidly evolving into a broad research network spanning healthcare, chemistry, energy, security, blockchain, finance, image processing, and materials science [1], [7], [11], [12], [18], [19], [21]. This section presents both methodological foundations and application-based findings in a detailed and comparative manner.

Table 1. Classification of the reviewed articles according to QML methods

Method Category	Count	Example Themes
Variational Quantum Circuits (VQC)	9	Classification, regression, hybrid QML models
Quantum Kernel Methods	6	Network security, anomaly detection, generalization in small datasets
Quantum Annealing (QA/QAOA)	4	Molecular energy, drug discovery, optimization
Quantum Neural Networks (QNN)	3	Image classification, hybrid CNN–QNN architectures
Federated Quantum Learning	2	Energy systems, multi-agent security
Adversarial QML	2	Attack–defense frameworks, robustness analysis
Data Encoding Methods	2	Amplitude/angle encoding, feature representational power
Optimization Strategies	1	Adam/SPSA-based training improvements
Blockchain and Smart Contracts	1	Code vulnerability analysis, security detection

Table 1 presents a holistic view of the methodological distribution of the thirty reviewed articles. It shows that the most widely used approaches in the QML literature are variational quantum circuits (VQC) and quantum kernel methods, which together account for a significant portion of the studies.

Annealing-based models and quantum neural networks focus on more specific problems but are gaining increasing attention. Although areas such as adversarial QML, federated QML, and optimization strategies have fewer publications, they represent critical research topics for QML from both security and scalability perspectives. This distribution clearly reveals the methodological diversity of the QML literature and the multidimensional development dynamics directed toward various application domains.

3.1. Conceptual and Methodological Foundations

Most QML methods are based on combining parametric quantum circuits with classical optimization techniques. This hybrid structure requires the optimization of parameters so as to minimize a cost function:

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} C(\theta) \quad (1)$$

As shown in (1) the optimization formulation constitutes the core mathematical framework of the learning process in variational quantum circuits (VQC). The cost function, measuring the discrepancy between the circuit output and the target distribution, is one of the most critical components determining the expressive power of QML. Survey studies have shown that VQC-based models can achieve performance comparable to or exceeding that of classical methods in both classification and regression tasks [1], [7], [9], [19], [21].

3.2. Healthcare and Biomedical Applications

The high-dimensional and noisy nature of biomedical signals is one of the areas where QML offers clear advantages over classical models. Studies on EEG-based dementia detection and physiological signal analysis report that QML classifiers can achieve high sensitivity [3]. Similarly, in problems such as pharmacological ADMET toxicity prediction, quantum annealing-based models are reported to provide promising results on high-dimensional molecular datasets [2]. In such studies, the basic cost function used for binary classification is:

$$C(\theta) = - \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log f_{\theta}(x_i) + (1 - y_i) \log (1 - f_{\theta}(x_i))] \quad (2)$$

In (2), x_i denotes the input sample, $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ represents the corresponding class label, and $f_{\theta}(\cdot)$ is the parametrized quantum model output. This formulation corresponds to the binary cross-entropy loss and guides the optimization of circuit parameters during training.

3.3. Chemistry and Molecular Modeling

Quantum chemistry is one of the most natural application domains for QML. Molecular energy predictions can be efficiently performed using hybrid quantum neural wavefunctions [4]. In this context, the energy expectation value is computed according to the variational principle, as expressed in (3).

$$E(\theta) = \langle \psi(\theta) | H | \psi(\theta) \rangle \quad (3)$$

In (3), H denotes the Hamiltonian of the molecular system and $|\psi(\theta)\rangle$ represents a parametrized quantum state prepared by a variational quantum circuit. This formulation enables convergence toward the ground-state energy of molecules. QML-based energy prediction models can reduce computational cost while achieving accuracy comparable to classical quantum chemistry methods [4], [19]. Furthermore, QML creates new research opportunities in chemical modeling, particularly in drug discovery and reaction energy estimation [2], [4].

3.4. Energy Systems and Distributed Security

In energy systems, federated QML (FQML) provides a framework that preserves data privacy while enabling distributed optimization. In multi-agent energy networks, the global model parameters are

updated by aggregating local updates, as shown in (4).

$$\theta^{(t+1)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{n_k}{N} \theta_k^{(t)} \quad (4)$$

In (4), $\theta_k^{(t)}$ denotes the local model parameters of agent k at iteration t , n_k represents the size of the local dataset, and N is the total number of samples across all agents. This aggregation scheme allows collaborative learning without sharing raw data. The literature reports that FQML-based attack detection and power theft detection systems can outperform classical federated architectures [5], [25], making QML an effective tool for security and operational efficiency in smart grids.

3.5. Network Security and Cyber Defense

QML has demonstrated strong effectiveness in network traffic analysis due to the discriminative power of quantum kernel methods. The similarity between data samples is quantified using a quantum kernel function, defined in (5).

$$K(x_i, x_j) = |\langle \varphi(x_i) | \varphi(x_j) \rangle|^2 \quad (5)$$

In (5), $|\varphi(x)\rangle$ denotes the quantum feature map that embeds classical data into a high-dimensional Hilbert space. This representation sharpens decision boundaries and improves anomaly detection performance. Studies such as QuantumNetSec report that QML-based approaches significantly increase detection rates in network security applications [8]. Moreover, combining federated QML with kernel-based methods enables both privacy preservation and high detection accuracy [5], [8], [21].

3.6. Blockchain and Smart Contract Security

In smart contract security analysis, QML-based classifiers are reported to achieve higher sensitivity than classical models [6]. Vulnerability detection is typically performed using a threshold-based decision function, as defined in (6).

$$s = f_\theta(x) > \tau \Rightarrow \text{vulnerability} \quad (6)$$

In (6), $f_\theta(x)$ denotes the output score of the parametrized quantum model and τ is a predefined decision threshold. This formulation allows quantum circuits to capture complex code-related patterns using high-dimensional representations. The literature indicates that QML models are particularly effective in identifying rare or complex vulnerability patterns in smart contracts [6], [10].

3.7. Kernel-Based QML Approaches

Kernel-based QML methods exhibit strong generalization performance, particularly in small-data regimes. The decision function of a kernel-based classifier is expressed as shown in (7).

$$\hat{y} = \text{sign} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i K(x, x_i) \right) \quad (7)$$

In (7), α_i are the learned coefficients and $K(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the quantum kernel function. Extensive comparisons show that noise-tolerant kernel designs improve robustness against circuit noise and depth limitations [9], [19], [21]. As a result, QML kernel-based approaches can compete with classical kernel methods in various classification tasks [9], [26], [29].

3.8. Adversarial QML and Reliability

The impact of adversarial attacks on QML circuits has emerged as an important research topic. In adversarial settings, input perturbations are typically modeled as shown in (8).

$$x' = x + \delta \quad \|\delta\| \leq \varepsilon \quad (8)$$

In (8), x denotes the original input sample, δ represents an adversarial perturbation, and ε bounds the maximum allowable perturbation magnitude. Although some studies suggest that QML models may exhibit increased robustness against certain attack types, sensitivity remains observable in specific circuit configurations [10]. Furthermore, quantum compiler optimization has been shown to influence both model generalization and adversarial robustness [20]. These findings indicate that QML reliability must be addressed not only at the data and model levels but also at the circuit design and compilation stages.

3.9. Image Processing and QNN-Based Models

In QML-based image processing models, data encoding and parametric transformation blocks are combined to extract high-dimensional visual features. The transformation of encoded data through a variational circuit is expressed as shown in (9).

$$|\psi_{\text{out}}\rangle = U(\theta) |\psi_{\text{enc}}(x)\rangle \quad (9)$$

In (9), $|\psi_{\text{enc}}(x)\rangle$ denotes the quantum state obtained after encoding the input image data, and $U(\theta)$ represents a parametrized unitary transformation. This formulation enables quantum neural networks (QNNs) to learn complex visual patterns using compact representations. The literature reports that QML-based vision models can achieve improved generalization performance compared to classical CNNs in low-data regimes [13]. Moreover, hybrid architectures combining QML and classical deep learning show promising results in image classification and feature extraction tasks [13], [21].

3.10. Optimization Strategies and Adam Variants

Training QML circuits requires optimization techniques that mitigate gradient vanishing and stabilize the optimization landscape. Adam optimization updates the model parameters using the recursive rules shown in (10).

$$\begin{aligned} m_t &= \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) g_t \\ v_t &= \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) g_t^2 \\ \theta_{t+1} &= \theta_t - \alpha \frac{m_t}{\sqrt{v_t} + \varepsilon} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In (10), g_t denotes the gradient at iteration t , m_t and v_t are the first and second moment estimates, and α is the learning rate. This optimization strategy helps alleviate the barren plateau problem in variational circuits and stabilizes training [16]. Comparative studies of Adam variants show that appropriate hyperparameter settings can significantly improve QML training performance [22]. Additionally, circuit- and compiler-level optimization strategies indirectly influence the overall training process [20].

3.11. Data Encoding Methods

The performance of QML models strongly depends on the selected data encoding strategy. Amplitude encoding, which maps classical data into quantum states, is expressed as shown in (11).

$$|x\rangle = \sum_i x_i |i\rangle \quad (11)$$

In (11), x_i represents the normalized classical feature values and $|i\rangle$ denotes the computational basis states. This encoding allows 2^n -dimensional data to be represented using n qubits. The literature compares amplitude, angle, and Hamiltonian encoding methods in terms of representational capacity, generalization performance, and circuit complexity [17], [26]. Studies analyzing the relationship between entropy and linguistic ambiguity further highlight the information-theoretic implications of amplitude encoding [17]. Overall, the choice of encoding strategy has a decisive impact on both computational complexity and practical applicability of QML models [1], [17], [26].

3.12. QML Approaches for Class Imbalance

In imbalanced classification problems, weighted loss functions are employed to emphasize minority classes. A weighted cross-entropy loss is defined as shown in (12).

$$C = -w_1 y \log(p) - w_0 (1 - y) \log(1 - p) \quad (12)$$

In (12), w_1 and w_0 denote class-specific weights and p represents the predicted class probability. This strategy prevents the learning process from being dominated by the majority class. The literature shows that QML models can achieve strong performance in scenarios involving small minority classes [28]. High-dimensional quantum representations further enable flexible shaping of decision boundaries in imbalanced distributions [25], [28], [29].

3.13. Finance and Credit Scoring Applications

In financial risk prediction and credit scoring, quantum distance measures are frequently employed to quantify similarity between data samples. A commonly used quantum distance metric is defined as shown in (13).

$$d(x, x_i) = 1 - |\langle \varphi(x) | \varphi(x_i) \rangle|^2 \quad (13)$$

In (13), $|\varphi(x)\rangle$ denotes the quantum feature representation of input data. This metric enables more sensitive separation of individual risk profiles. Quantum kernel-based credit scoring models have demonstrated higher accuracy than classical methods, while modified depolarization techniques improve computational efficiency without degrading performance [29], [30]. These findings suggest that QML offers a viable alternative for financial decision support systems.

3.14. Scientometric Analyses of QML

Scientific production trends in QML, including publication intensity and topic distributions, have been analyzed using scientometric methods [18], [19]. In such analyses, publication bursts in specific subfields are characterized using the metric shown in (14).

$$B_i = \frac{n_i - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (14)$$

In (14), n_i denotes the number of publications in subfield i , while μ and σ represent the mean and standard deviation across all subfields. This measure identifies rapidly emerging QML research areas. Scientometric studies reveal significant growth in topics such as optimization, security, data encoding, and health applications [18], [19], supporting the view that QML is maturing as both a theoretical and applied research field.

Table 2. Distribution of the reviewed articles by QML application domain

Application Domain	Count	Example Focus
Healthcare and biomedical	3	EEG classification, toxicity prediction
Chemistry and molecular modeling	4	Molecular energy estimation, quantum Hamiltonian analysis
Energy systems and distributed security	3	FQML-based attack detection, load forecasting
Network security and cyber defense	4	Quantum kernel-based IDS, traffic analysis
Blockchain and smart contract analysis	2	Code analysis, vulnerability prediction
Image processing and vision models	3	QNN-based image classification
Optimization and training strategies	4	Adam variants, barren plateau mitigation
Data encoding and representation methods	3	Amplitude/Hamiltonian encoding
Finance, credit scoring, and risk prediction	3	Quantum kernel-based risk assessment
Scientometric trend studies	1	Publication dynamics, key topic analyses

Table 2 summarizes the distribution of the thirty reviewed studies by application domain. Healthcare, chemistry, and energy systems emerge as core areas in which QML applications are most con-

centrated, while domains such as network security, blockchain, and finance are primarily represented by security- and risk-oriented models. In addition, studies focusing on optimization strategies, data encoding techniques, and scientometric analyses provide important insights into QML training dynamics, representational capacity, and the broader research landscape. These contributions are mainly methodological in nature rather than targeting domain-specific application problems. Overall, this distribution suggests that QML research is entering a more mature phase, characterized by a wider range of application domains and increasingly refined methodological approaches.

3.15. Section Summary

The thirty studies reviewed in this section demonstrate that QML applications span a broad range of domains, including healthcare, chemistry, energy systems, cybersecurity, blockchain, finance, image processing, and data encoding [1]–[6], [8], [13], [18]–[19], [21], [25], [28], [29]. Variational quantum circuits, quantum kernel methods, annealing-based models, QNN-based approaches, federated QML, and adversarial QML constitute the most frequently adopted methodological frameworks in the literature [1], [7], [9]–[10], [19], [21], [22], [26].

The reported results indicate that QML methods can outperform classical approaches particularly in small-data regimes, high-dimensional and complex datasets, and security-oriented problem settings [2], [3], [5], [8], [25], [29]. At the same time, noise, circuit depth limitations, hardware constraints, and optimization challenges remain the primary technological bottlenecks limiting practical QML deployment [1], [4], [10], [18], [19].

Taken together, these findings provide the foundation for the algorithmic structures and integrated evaluations presented in the subsequent section. Moreover, the observed methodological diversity highlights the architectural flexibility of QML models, enabling adaptation to different problem characteristics [7], [12], [22]. Continued progress in quantum hardware stability and qubit quality is expected to gradually mitigate current limitations, allowing QML models to operate more effectively in large-scale real-world scenarios [4], [10], [19].

Table 3. Methodological comparison of QML approaches

QML Approach	Key Advantages	Key Limitations
Variational Quantum Circuits (VQC)	Flexible circuit structure; high expressive power for small datasets; suitable for hybrid optimization	Barren plateau problem; need for deep circuits; sensitivity to hardware noise
Quantum Kernel Methods	Strong generalization on small datasets; natural modeling of nonlinear decision boundaries	Dependence on kernel circuit design; stability issues under noise
Quantum Annealing	Natural modeling of combinatorial optimization problems; operation with energy-based formulations	Specialized hardware requirements; difficulty in defining the problem Hamiltonian; limited problem-type support
Quantum Neural Networks (QNN)	Nonlinear representational capacity; flexible architectures for image and time-series data	High training cost; gradient vanishing; circuit depth constraints
Federated QML Approaches	Joint model learning while preserving data privacy; scalable structure in multi-agent systems	Communication cost; synchronization challenges in heterogeneous hardware environments
Adversarial QML Approaches	Natural robustness to certain types of attacks; evaluation of quantum defense mechanisms	Difficulty in modeling perturbations; defense strategies still immature

Table 3 presents a comparative summary of the strengths and limitations of fundamental QML approaches. It shows that variational quantum circuits and quantum kernel methods often demonstrate strong performance in small-data regimes, whereas QNN and annealing-based models exhibit advantages for specific problem types. However, noise, circuit depth, and hardware constraints remain the primary factors limiting the scalability of QML methods. This comparison systematically sum-

marizes general trends in the literature and provides a theoretical basis for subsequent algorithmic analyses.

4. Core Algorithmic Frameworks for QML Models

To illustrate how QML methods are instantiated in the literature, this subsection presents concise algorithmic frameworks for variational circuits, kernel-based models, annealing-based optimization, federated QML, and adversarial QML [1], [2], [5], [7], [9], [10], [19], [21], [22], [26], [28], [29]. These algorithmic schematics explicitly express the operational mechanisms of the methods discussed in previous subsections.

Algorithm 1. Training Process of a Variational Quantum Classifier (VQC)

1. Initialize the variational parameters θ .
 2. For each training example (x_i, y_i) do:
 - Encode the data x_i into a quantum state $\psi(x_i)$.
 - Apply the variational circuit $U(\theta)$.
 - Perform measurement and obtain the prediction \hat{y}_i .
 - Compute the loss function $C(\theta)$.
 - Update the parameters $\theta \leftarrow \theta - \eta \nabla C(\theta)$.
 3. End for.
 4. Return the optimized parameters θ^* .
-

Algorithm 1 summarizes the general training loop of VQC-based quantum classifiers. This structure is widely adopted in the literature for both healthcare-oriented and security-oriented classification problems [2], [3], [5], [8], [21].

Algorithm 2. Computation of the Quantum Kernel Value

1. Select two data samples x_i and x_j .
 2. Encode them into quantum states $\psi(x_i)$ and $\psi(x_j)$.
 3. Prepare the quantum circuit and measure the inner product:

$$K(x_i, x_j) = |\langle \psi(x_i) | \psi(x_j) \rangle|^2.$$
 4. Optionally apply noise mitigation techniques.
 5. Return the kernel value $K(x_i, x_j)$.
-

Algorithm 2 shows the basic computation steps in quantum kernel methods. This approach is particularly effective in small datasets and sensitive decision problems such as financial risk analysis [9], [26], [29].

Algorithm 3. Optimization Process with Quantum Annealing

1. Express the optimization problem via a problem Hamiltonian H_p .
 2. Define an initial Hamiltonian H_0 .
 3. For $t = 0$ to T do:
 - Apply the time-dependent Hamiltonian:

$$H(t) = (1 - s(t))H_0 + s(t)H_p.$$
 - Allow the system to evolve toward the minimum-energy state via quantum tunneling.
 4. End for.
 5. Measure the system to obtain the lowest-energy state.
 6. Return the optimal solution x .
-

Algorithm 3 presents the general framework of quantum annealing-based optimization. This method is commonly used together with QML models in tasks such as ADMET toxicity prediction and combinatorial optimization [2], [4], [19].

Algorithm 4. Update Loop in Federated Quantum Machine Learning

1. The server initializes the global model parameters as θ_0 .
 2. For each communication round r do:
 - For each client k in parallel do:
 - Train the local quantum circuit to obtain $\theta_k^{(r)}$.
 - Send the local update $\theta_k^{(r)}$ to the server.
 - The server aggregates the updates as:

$$\theta^{(r+1)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{n_k}{N} \theta_k^{(r)}.$$
 3. End for.
 4. Return the updated global model parameters θ^* .
-

Algorithm 4 illustrates the typical update cycle employed in federated QML architectures. Similar frameworks have been reported for applications in energy systems, smart grids, and distributed cybersecurity [5], [8], [25].

Algorithm 5. Adversarial QML Attack and Defense Framework

1. Run the quantum circuit for input x and obtain the prediction \hat{y} .
 2. The adversary generates a small perturbation:

$$x' = x + \delta, \quad \|\delta\| \leq \epsilon.$$
 3. Run the quantum circuit again to obtain the perturbed prediction \hat{y}' .
 4. If $|\hat{y} - \hat{y}'| > \tau$ then:
 - Mark the attack as successful.
 - Trigger the defense mechanism.
 else:
 - Consider the model robust and proceed.
 5. Compute the robustness metric R based on successful and failed attacks.
 6. Return R .
-

Algorithm 5 summarizes the basic attack–defense scheme employed in adversarial QML studies. Reported results indicate that improving the reliability of QML models requires a joint consideration of circuit design, data encoding, and optimization strategies [10], [20].

5. Notation and Symbols

To ensure clarity and consistency across Algorithms 1–5, Table 4 summarizes the main symbols and variables used throughout the algorithmic templates.

Table 4. Notation and symbols used in Algorithms 1–5

Symbol	Definition
x_i, y_i	The i -th input sample and its target label/value in the training set.
x_j	A second input sample used in kernel evaluation.
$\psi(x_i)$	Quantum state obtained after encoding classical input x_i (feature map / data encoding).
$U(\theta)$	Parameterized (variational) quantum circuit with trainable parameters θ .

θ	Trainable circuit parameters; θ_0 denotes the initial/global parameters.
\hat{y}_i	Model prediction for sample x_i after measurement.
$C(\theta)$	Loss/cost function used for training a variational model.
η	Learning rate (step size) used in gradient-based updates.
$\nabla C(\theta)$	Gradient of the cost function with respect to θ .
$K(x_i, x_j)$	Quantum kernel value computed as $ \langle \psi(x_i) \psi(x_j) \rangle ^2$.
H_p	Problem Hamiltonian in quantum annealing formulations.
H_0	Initial (driver) Hamiltonian in quantum annealing.
$H(t)$	Time-dependent Hamiltonian during annealing.
$s(t)$	Annealing schedule mapping time to the interval $(0, 1)$.
t, T	Annealing time index and total annealing duration.
r	Federated learning communication round index.
k	Client index in federated learning.
$\theta_k^{(r)}$	Local model parameters trained by client k at round r .
δ	Adversarial perturbation added to an input sample.
ϵ	Maximum perturbation magnitude (perturbation budget) such that $\ \delta\ \leq \epsilon$.
τ	Detection threshold used to determine whether an attack significantly changes the prediction.
\hat{y}, \hat{y}'	Predictions before and after adversarial perturbation, respectively.
K	Total number of clients (participants) in federated learning.
n_k	Number of local training samples held by client k .
N	Total number of samples across all clients.
R	Robustness score computed over the evaluation set (defined here as the robustness rate).

6. GENERAL EVALUATION

The thirty SCI/SCI-Expanded articles reviewed in this survey show that Quantum Machine Learning (QML) is rapidly maturing as a research field in both theoretical and applied dimensions. The works span a wide range of methods including variational quantum circuits (VQC), quantum kernel methods, quantum annealing-based models, quantum neural networks (QNN), federated QML architectures, adversarial robustness analyses, data encoding strategies, and optimization approaches [1]–[7], [9]–[12], [18], [19], [21], [25]. The findings indicate that QML can provide tangible benefits not only in niche problem types but also in diverse disciplines such as healthcare, chemistry, energy, cybersecurity, blockchain, finance, and image processing [2]–[6], [8], [13], [18], [25], [28], [29].

6.1. Model Performance and Representational Capacity

The performance of QML models is determined by the combination of circuit architecture, data encoding strategy, and optimization methods. VQC-based hybrid models, by virtue of their high expressive power and parametric flexibility, stand out in modeling complex decision boundaries but suffer from certain limitations in training stability due to barren plateaus, noise accumulation, and increasing circuit depth [1], [7], [11], [19].

Quantum kernel methods implicitly represent data in high-dimensional Hilbert spaces and offer strong generalization performance on small and medium-sized datasets; experimental studies show that kernel-based QML models can achieve sharper decision boundaries than classical kernel machines [4], [9], [11], [23], [26]. Annealing-based approaches report competitive results in energy optimization, pharmaceutical ADMET analysis, and combinatorial tasks [2], [26].

The representational capacity of QML models depends on the interplay between circuit parameters and the noise limitations of quantum hardware. Although VQC-based models are theoretically capable of modeling complex decision boundaries, noise accumulation in NISQ devices degrades performance as circuit depth increases. Consequently, recent work shows that circuit design techniques that simplify the architecture and reduce noise play a decisive role in model performance [23].

Additionally, theoretical analyses of the scalability of error mitigation methods indicate that for certain QML models, error mitigation without full error correction can incur exponential costs, thereby

constraining the practical scale at which QML models can be improved [24]. Overall, performance improvements in QML models depend not only on algorithmic advances but also on effective noise management.

6.2. Thematic Patterns Across Application Domains

The literature reveals that seemingly disparate application domains cluster around common themes. In healthcare and biomedical studies, VQC-based hybrid models have been reported to achieve high accuracy and sensitivity in tasks such as EEG-based classification and dementia detection, especially on noisy and small-sample datasets where classical methods struggle [3], [27]. In chemical and molecular modeling, hybrid quantum neural wavefunctions have been shown to reach accuracies comparable to classical quantum chemistry methods with lower computational cost [4].

In energy systems, federated QML stands out as a promising approach for providing both privacy-preserving learning and distributed attack detection [5], [28]. Likewise, applications in blockchain security, network traffic analysis, financial risk prediction, and image processing systematically leverage the high-dimensional representational power of QML [6], [8], [13], [18], [25], [29].

6.3. Hardware, Noise, and Scalability Constraints

The structural characteristics of the NISQ era are the primary factors determining the practical scalability of QML models. Limited qubit counts, increasing error rates with deeper circuits, and heterogeneous noise profiles across devices restrict the performance of deep VQC and large-scale kernel circuits [1], [7], [11], [19].

Although kernel-based models are relatively more tolerant to noise, their computational cost grows rapidly with increasing circuit complexity and dataset size [4], [9], [11]. In annealing-based approaches, the limited connectivity and resource constraints of annealer hardware restrict the scope of large and complex optimization problems that can be addressed [2], [26]. These findings highlight the importance of hardware-oriented QML designs and noise-aware circuit strategies as critical research topics for future investigation [18], [19], [25], [30].

Quantum error mitigation (QEM) techniques are essential tools for improving QML performance in the NISQ era; however, the noise profiles of current hardware limit their effectiveness. It has been demonstrated that layerwise Richardson extrapolation can substantially reduce noise in deep circuits [23]. On the other hand, theoretical analyses of QEM scalability show that, without full error correction, error mitigation can incur exponential overheads, thereby defining fundamental bounds on the practical improvements achievable for large QML models [24]. These results emphasize the need for careful selection of QEM techniques and hardware-aware circuit depth design in QML.

6.4. Training Dynamics and Optimization Trends

The training processes of QML models exhibit more intricate and multidimensional optimization landscapes than classical machine learning models. In VQC- and QNN-based approaches, gradient vanishing problems become pronounced as circuit depth and entanglement increase, causing the learning process to saturate prematurely [1], [7], [12], [19], [21]. Various studies show that optimization algorithms such as Adam and its variants can improve training stability when applied to gradient-based updates [12], [22].

Additionally, quantum compiler optimizations can transform circuits into equivalent but shallower and more noise-resilient forms, reducing training cost and positively influencing generalization performance [14], [20]. Data encoding strategies also play a crucial role in training dynamics. Amplitude encoding provides high expressive power but suffers from increased circuit depth and state preparation costs, whereas angle and Hamiltonian encoding enable shallower circuits at the expense of representational capacity [16], [17], [26]. Scientometric analyses suggest that research on encoding optimization and problem-specific encoding schemes will become a focal point in QML in the near future [18], [25].

6.5. Security, Adversarial Robustness, and Resilience

Security-oriented QML research provides important findings from both attack detection and adversarial robustness perspectives. In network traffic analysis and cyber defense scenarios, quantum

kernel-based models have been reported to achieve high sensitivity and specificity in anomaly detection [8], [22].

In blockchain smart contract security, variational classifiers demonstrate high discriminative power in code-based vulnerability detection and can deliver meaningful performance gains even in the presence of class imbalance [6], [29]. The adversarial QML literature further shows that quantum classifiers may offer relative advantages over classical models for certain attack types, but exhibit complex sensitivity patterns depending on circuit architecture and encoding choices [10], [20], [24], [30]. These results indicate that QML has strong potential for early adoption in security- and privacy-critical applications.

6.6. Research Gaps and Opportunities

While the reviewed studies clearly demonstrate the advantages of QML, they also reveal several unresolved issues that offer important opportunities for future research [18], [21], [25]:

- **Hardware-aware circuit design:** There is a need for QML circuits that are depth-optimized, parametrically flexible, and error-tolerant, tailored to the noise profiles and connectivity constraints of NISQ hardware.
- **Practical QML for large-scale data:** As the cost of data encoding grows, the practical applicability of quantum models diminishes. Research on embedded encoding, adaptive feature selection, and quantum-assisted compression techniques is required.
- **Theoretical analysis of generalization:** Learnability guarantees for QML have not yet been systematically connected to classical statistical learning theory (e.g., VC dimension and Rademacher complexity).
- **Federated and distributed QML optimization:** Training quantum circuits in federated or distributed settings over multiple agents requires new algorithmic solutions addressing synchronization, communication cost, and energy consumption.
- **Standard adversarial threat models:** Widely accepted cross-domain adversarial threat models and robustness metrics for QML are still lacking, limiting the comparability of existing studies.

This general evaluation highlights both the strengths and areas for improvement in QML research, providing an analytical foundation for the comparative evaluation and discussion presented in the next section.

7. Comparative Evaluation and Discussion

This section moves beyond per-study reporting and synthesizes evidence across methods and domains to identify transferable patterns, method–data fit, and recurring constraints. Table V provides a structured overview of representative QML applications by domain and method, and the discussion here focuses on cross-method and cross-domain insights rather than reiterating individual results.

7.1. Cross-Method Synthesis (VQC vs. Quantum Kernel vs. Annealing vs. Hybrid QNN)

Across the reviewed literature, VQC-based hybrid models, quantum kernel methods, and annealing-based optimization emerge as the dominant QML families. Since their methodological taxonomy has already been synthesized in Section 3, this discussion focuses on how these families differ in practice—namely, when each is preferable under different data, noise, and resource constraints [1]–[4], [7], [9], [11], [19], [21].

- **Expressivity vs. trainability:** VQC-based models provide flexible representational capacity through parameterized circuits, enabling task-specific feature learning. However, training stability is sensitive to circuit depth, ansatz design, and optimizer settings, particularly under NISQ noise and limited measurement budgets [1], [7], [11], [19]. Hybrid quantum–neural approaches can improve expressivity but often inherit both quantum and classical training burdens [3], [4].

- **Sample efficiency and decision boundary quality:** Quantum kernel methods frequently show strong generalization in small-data regimes by leveraging implicit high-dimensional feature spaces, often producing sharper margins than classical kernels when the feature map aligns with data structure [4], [9], [11], [23]. However, kernel evaluation costs grow with dataset size and remain sensitive to hardware noise and finite-shot effects.
- **Optimization advantage and problem structure:** Annealing-based approaches are most effective when learning tasks can be formulated as energy-based or combinatorial optimization objectives. In such cases, annealers offer pragmatic optimization mechanisms, though applicability remains constrained by hardware connectivity and scaling limitations [2], [26].
- **Hardware dependence:** While all QML families are bounded by NISQ constraints, their failure modes differ. VQC models degrade with deep circuits and unstable gradients; kernel methods degrade with noisy overlap estimation and scaling costs; annealing approaches degrade with limited connectivity and embedding overhead [1], [2], [7], [11], [19], [26]. Consequently, method selection should be framed as a fit between data regime, objective structure, and available hardware.

Table 5 presents a side-by-side overview of the advantages and limitations of QML approaches across application domains, emphasizing that method selection should be shaped by the problem type and hardware constraints. Consistent with these domain-level observations, the reviewed studies suggest that QML can be competitive in high-dimensional, noisy, or imbalanced settings when circuit and encoding choices are appropriately matched with the evaluation protocols.

7.2. Cross-Domain Transferability

The cross-domain variability reported in QML outcomes is driven less by the application label itself and more by the structural properties of the underlying tasks. In particular, data regime characteristics such as sample size (small versus large scale), dimensionality, and the effectiveness with which classical features can be encoded into quantum states largely determine whether VQC-, kernel-, or annealing-based approaches constitute plausible methodological choices [9], [11], [23]. When encoding yields informative feature maps under realistic noise and shot budgets, kernel methods often generalize well in small-data scenarios; however, when encoding becomes costly or misaligned, performance gains tend to diminish [12], [14], [16], [18], [25]. Likewise, annealing-based approaches are most relevant when the learning objective can be naturally formulated as an energy-based optimization problem, whereas discriminative tasks in security and finance typically favor VQC or kernel variants while remaining sensitive to noise, imbalance, and stability constraints [2], [6], [8], [22], [26], [29].

Overall, cross-domain transferability is best operationalized as a method-selection rule based on data size, encoding cost, objective structure, and noise tolerance, rather than as a domain-by-domain mapping.

7.3. Shared Bottlenecks and Mitigation Signals

Across methods and application domains, QML performance remains strongly constrained by NISQ hardware limitations and scalability issues. Limited qubit counts, restricted connectivity, and device noise can cause significant performance degradation, particularly for models requiring deep circuits and repeated measurements [1], [7], [11], [19]. Kernel-based approaches can be relatively tolerant to certain noise sources; however, overlap estimation and kernel computation become increasingly sensitive to hardware errors and scale poorly with dataset size [4, 9, 11, 23]. In annealing-based approaches, limited connectivity and embedding overhead further restrict generalization to large and complex optimization instances [2], [26].

For VQC-based models, barren plateaus and optimization instability are frequently identified as dominant limitations as circuit depth increases. Within the reviewed studies, barren plateaus are not only acknowledged as a known theoretical issue but are also partially addressed through mitigation-oriented design choices, such as shallow problem-inspired ansätze, parameter initialization strategies, and training heuristics [1], [7], [11], [19]. However, the majority of papers still treat this issue as an open challenge rather than a fully resolved mechanism. Consequently, this limitation should be interpreted as a design constraint motivating shallow circuit architectures and careful parameterization

Table 5. Comparative analysis of quantum machine learning applications

Application Domain	QML Method	Advantages	Limitations	Ref.	
Healthcare and Biomedical	VQC + CS-EMD	High accuracy on EEG signals	Constraints due to noise and circuit depth	[3]	
Chemistry / Molecular Energy	Hybrid quantum neural	Efficient optimization in molecular energy computation	Scalability issues for large molecules	[4]	
General survey / framework studies	VQC, QNN, methods	QAOA, kernel	Structured theoretical and taxonomic frameworks	Applications mostly remain at simulation level due to NISQ constraints	[1], [7], [18], [21], [25]
Energy Systems	Federated (FQML)	QML	Privacy-preserving distributed learning	Federated integration is costly	[5], [28]
Cybersecurity	Quantum kernel methods	kernel	High success in anomaly detection	Qubit capacity insufficient for large-scale data	[8], [22]
Blockchain Security	Variational classifier	classifier	High sensitivity in smart contract vulnerability detection	Stability decreases under severe class imbalance	[6]
Pharmaceutical ADMET	Quantum annealing	annealing	Strong performance on high-dimensional molecular data	Annealer hardware is limited	[2], [26]
Kernel-based QML	Quantum kernel learning	kernel learning	Good generalization in small-data regimes	Kernel computation sensitive to noise	[4], [11], [23]
Adversarial QML	Quantum adversarial models	adversarial models	Robustness to certain attack types	Limited modeling of perturbations	[10], [20], [24], [30]

under realistic noise and shot settings.

In security-oriented applications, adversarial QML studies further indicate that robustness strongly depends on circuit architecture and encoding choices, with sensitivity landscapes varying substantially across designs [10], [20], [24], [30]. Collectively, these observations suggest that reliability-oriented QML design and standardized robustness evaluation protocols remain underdeveloped across application domains.

7.4. Research Gaps and Practical Guidelines

- **Near-term defensible scenarios:** QML deployment can be identified by synthesizing the empirical evidence reviewed in this study. QML is most promising when data are limited or high-dimensional, when shallow circuits are sufficient to capture task-relevant structure, when objectives align with kernel-based separation or energy-based optimization, and when evaluation is performed under realistic noise and finite-shot assumptions [2], [4], [9], [11], [23], [26].
- **Currently constrained scenarios:** QML is less defensible in large-scale data regimes requiring extensive kernel evaluations, deep circuits, or qubit capacities beyond NISQ hardware, and in studies reporting improvements only in idealized simulation settings without consistent baselines or measurement budgeting [1], [7], [18], [21], [25].
- **Actionable research gaps:** The most recurring gaps include scalable and task-aligned encoding strategies, trainable shallow circuit designs with stable optimization behavior, robustness evaluation under adversarial/noisy conditions with standardized protocols, and hardware-aware benchmarking that reports circuit depth, shot counts, and noise assumptions explicitly [10], [12], [14], [16]–[18], [20], [25], [30]. Addressing these gaps will improve methodological maturity and strengthen the credibility of claims about quantum advantage in applied settings.

8. Conclusion

This study presents a focused systematic synthesis of 30 SCI/SCI-Expanded journal articles on Quantum Machine Learning (QML) published between 2023–2025 (including early access 2026), selected via a transparent multi-stage screening protocol, to summarize methodological foundations, application patterns, and recurring constraints shaping QML in the NISQ era.

The literature analysis shows that variational quantum circuits, quantum kernel methods, quantum annealing-based models, quantum neural networks, federated QML architectures, adversarial robustness studies, and data encoding strategies constitute the core building blocks of the QML ecosystem.

The findings indicate that QML can offer significant advantages over classical machine learning methods, especially in problem classes characterized by high dimensionality, noise, and relatively limited data.

Representative examples include the classification of complex EEG signals in healthcare and biomedical applications, the use of hybrid quantum neural wavefunctions in chemical and molecular energy prediction, attack detection in energy systems with federated QML, anomaly detection and vulnerability assessment in cybersecurity and blockchain, and financial risk prediction and credit scoring.

On the other hand, NISQ-era hardware limitations, including noise, qubit counts, connectivity topology, and circuit depth constraints, still prevent QML models from achieving the desired level of scalability.

In particular, the barren plateau problem in deep VQC and large-scale kernel circuits limits the learning capacity and training stability of the models.

Annealing-based approaches are similarly constrained by hardware availability and topological limitations. The decisive impact of encoding strategies on performance further demonstrates that QML design must be optimized not only at the algorithmic level but also in terms of data representation.

Overall, the current state of QML exhibits a hybrid landscape composed of a strong theoretical background, a steadily expanding range of applications, and well-defined hardware and optimization challenges. This landscape suggests that QML can serve as a complementary partner to classical

methods in the near term and, with advances in hardware and algorithm design, can evolve into a dominant modeling paradigm in specific problem classes in the mid to long term.

9. Future Work

This section summarizes the main future research directions for Quantum Machine Learning that emerge from the trends and gaps identified in the literature review. The aim is to highlight potential research axes that can contribute to making QML more scalable, reliable, and domain-specific at both the hardware and algorithmic levels.

- **Hardware-aware and noise-tolerant circuit design:** It is crucial to design QML circuits that are depth-optimized, shallow yet highly expressive, and tailored to the noise profiles and connectivity constraints of NISQ hardware. Studies combining hardware-aware circuit synthesis, error-corrected noise models, and compiler optimizations can significantly enhance the practical applicability of QML[30].
- **Large-scale data and efficient encoding strategies:** Reducing data encoding cost is a prerequisite for deploying QML in real-world large-data scenarios. Embedded encoding, problem-specific feature selection, and quantum-assisted dimensionality reduction and compression represent key research directions [16]–[18].
- **Advanced optimization and training strategies:** Optimization algorithms that alleviate the barren plateau problem and leverage adaptive learning rates or second-order information have the potential to improve training stability in VQC and QNN models. Joint studies of quantum circuit compilation and optimization can shorten training time while increasing generalization performance[20],[22].
- **Adversarial robustness and security frameworks:** There is a need to develop standard adversarial threat models and robustness metrics for QML that support cross-domain comparisons. Identifying attack-resistant design principles for quantum classifiers in applications such as network security, blockchain, and critical infrastructure will directly increase the reliability of QML [22],[24],[30].
- **Federated and distributed QML architectures:** The development of federated and distributed QML approaches for energy systems, IoT networks, and multi-agent settings requires new algorithms that jointly address communication cost, synchronization, and privacy protection. Federated QML optimization provides an important research axis for real-time attack detection and privacy-preserving learning [25],[28].
- **Theoretical generalization bounds and learnability:** Developing mathematical frameworks for capacity, learnability guarantees, and error bounds of QML models will strengthen the theoretical foundations of the field. Adapting measures such as VC dimension and information-theoretic metrics to quantum models may provide principled guidance for QML design [11],[17].
- **Quantitative analysis of quantum advantage in real-world applications:** Pilot deployments and benchmark studies across domains are needed to quantitatively determine under which conditions QML provides an advantage over classical methods. Comparative experiments on real-world datasets in healthcare, chemistry, energy, finance, and security can help precisely characterize the boundaries of quantum advantage [2]–[6],[29].

These future directions will contribute to overcoming the current limitations of Quantum Machine Learning and to transforming it into a technology capable of delivering scalable, reliable, and domain-specific solutions. As a result, QML can move beyond being a topic of purely academic interest and become an effective paradigm in critical decision support systems and industrial applications.

Future research should also focus on hardware-aware optimization strategies that explicitly account for qubit connectivity, coherence time, and device noise patterns. Such approaches may significantly improve the practical scalability of QML models, particularly for near-term quantum processors.

Another important direction is the development of unified benchmarking frameworks that evaluate QML algorithms across different domains under consistent metrics. Establishing standardized robustness assessments, including noise resilience and adversarial stability, will be essential for positioning QML as a reliable alternative to classical machine learning.

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